

Welcome to the July newsletter, lots of news and summer reading for you.
Enjoy!

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Solent University LNL James Steele

Spotlight on open research at Solent University

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights the work of James Steele at Solent University in Southampton. James describes his work in teaching and research support and lists a range of free open source quantitative and qualitative analysis programs that you may be interested in. You can read all about these [here](#). He has also been busy planning substantial changes to undergraduate dissertation modules to incorporate open research practices.

Stop Press: Solent University are currently making widespread redundancies as a result of financial difficulties. Unfortunately, James is being made redundant and will leave his post at Solent at the end of July 2024. It is now unlikely that the new dissertation module will be implemented there. We are hoping James can make some aspects of his dissertation plans available online (a recent talk he gave about the planned module is available here: <https://osf.io/387hk/>). We will keep you posted on this. In the meantime, if you know of any job opportunities in the South or South East (or hybrid/remote) please contact James.

Notes from Newcastle LNL retreat

Dolly Coates, the UKRN project Coordinator, has written up her notes from the LNL retreat held at Newcastle University in June 2024. These can be found here <https://osf.io/68r3n> During the retreat LNL Dave Smailes talked about his successful application for internal Research Culture funding. If you would like a copy of his application, please contact Dave. Read LNL Sam Westwood's blog about the event [here](#).

UKRN videos

We're currently working with the film company WANDER to edit the two videos filmed during the retreat and hope to be able to share these with you soon.

University of Leeds LNL Eike Rinke

LNL wins award

Huge congratulations to the University of Leeds LNL Eike Rinke who has won an Open Research Practices award as part of the Leeds Research Culture Awards 2024.

Eike says

I am honoured and grateful to receive this award for my efforts to embed Open Research values and practices into the research culture at Leeds. This achievement is truly a collective effort. Within this, the community, resources, and inspiration I have found in UKRN have been a major force behind the community and awareness-building activities that the award recognises. I see it also as an award for the UKRN community that should motivate us to continue our important work as Local Network Leads across the UK. Let us keep at it!

Other national Reproducibility Networks

The UKRN is one of an increasing number of [national Reproducibility Networks](#). Recently the Community Project gathered RN representatives from 10 countries (Austria, [Brazil](#), [Belgium](#), [Croatia](#), [Germany](#), [Italy](#), [Norway](#), [Spain](#), [Switzerland](#), [UK](#)) for their first in-person meeting in Berlin. Several more country and regional representatives ([Africa](#), Belgium, Brazil, [France](#), [Netherlands](#), [Slovakia](#)) joined part of the meeting online. You can read about this event [here](#).

And for more insights into another Reproducibility Network, here is an [interview](#) with Michiel de Boer, founder of the Dutch Reproducibility Network.

Resources

[Directory of Open Access Books](#)

The Directory of Open Access Books is a community-driven service that indexes and provides access to scholarly, peer-reviewed open access books

and helps users to find trusted open access book publishers. All DOAB services are free of charge and all data is freely available.

[The Open Book Collective](#)

The Open Book Collective brings together publishers, publishing service providers, and scholarly libraries to secure the diversity and financial futures of open access book production and dissemination. They foster the sustainability of open infrastructures, such as repositories and book publishing software.

Read more [here](#)

Games time

Do you know your alpha helices from your beta sheets? Get ready to play [Foldit](#), a one-of-a-kind protein folding computer game developed by university scientists. By playing Foldit, you can contribute to advanced research on human health, cutting-edge bioengineering, and the inner workings of biology. Read more about the science involved [here](#).

Newsletter editor wanted

We are keen to make this newsletter sustainable and need your help to do this. Would you like to become an editor or contribute articles? Get in touch and we'll support you in making this a reality contact@ukrn.org
